

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FEATURE SELECTION METHODS IN HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION

Adaobi Grace Nwosu

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Rivers State University, Npkolu Oroworukwo,
Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15697732>

Abstract: This research presents a comparative analysis of several filter-based feature selections (FS) methods for improved prediction accuracy with most discriminant features to overcome the curse of dimensionality in Human Activity Recognition (HAR). Specifically, this work analyzes which features are most relevant for activity and investigates which classifier provides the best accuracy with those features. The performances of five filter-based feature selection(FS) methods (Information Gain(IG), Gain Ratio(GR), Chi-Square(CS), ReliefF (RfF), Correlation-based feature selection(CFS),) are evaluated using 6 machine learning classifiers (Naive Bayes(NB), Random Forest(RF), Support Vector Machine(SVM), K nearest neighbor (KNN), decision tree(CJ45) and Multi-Layer Perception(MLP)) with UCI publicly available dataset to test the comparisons. The results demonstrate improved accuracy with less features as well as improved performance of classifiers, RF and Relief yielding the best accuracy of 95.5%.

Keywords—Feature Selection, Filter-Based, Human Activity Recognition, Smartphone, Feature Ranking.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Due to exponential increase in production of data, high dimensions' data are common and leads to prevalence of noise, irrelevant and redundant data (Venkatesh & Anuradha, 2019). However, more features extracted does not mean improvement in the classification accuracy, since most feature can be irrelevant, redundant and constitutes noise, which affects classifier accuracy (Capela et al. 2015). Feature Selection(FS) removes irrelevant features i.e features that adds no information to the prediction (Capela et al. 2015,) and redundant features i.e those once that do not provide additional information than the currently selected features(Khaire & Dhanalakshmi ,2019) (Wang et al. 2018). FS is used to overcome the problem of curse of dimensionality. i.e number of features far more than the number of instances (Capela et al. 2015) (Wang et al. 2019). It selects the most discriminant features to be used for training the model, reduce model building time, model over-fitting (Khaire & Dhanalakshmi, 2019), reduce computational overload, storage space (Khaire & Dhanalakshmi,2019) and enhance accuracy (Wang et al. 2018). Based on evaluation criteria FS methods are classified into filter method, wrapper method, embedded method, and hybrid method. Wrapper method depends on the classifiers (Capela et al. 2015), the best subset of features is selected based on the result of the classifiers. They are computationally more expensive than filter method due to repeated steps and cross validation, but more accurate than the filter method (Venkatesh & Anuradha, 2019). Embedded

approach is made up of combination of filter and wrapper based, hence, the speed of filter based is combined with the high accuracy of wrapper-based to give the embedded approach (Wang et al. 2018). In filter method, features are assigned score value using statistical measures such as correlation, information gain, and are sorted in descending order and assigned ranking for the features (Wang et al. 2018) (Jamabi & Kadhim, 2018). Feature ranking advantage is that it requires only the computations and sorting of the scores of each feature subset (GAO Et Al. 2010). After scoring features, features subset is selected either by selecting features greater than a threshold or select the top N (N is user defined) features with the highest scores (Chan et al. 2020). Filter-based method do not consider the correlation between the independent variables while selecting the features. (Venkatesh & Anuradh, 2019)(Jamabi & Kadhim, 2018). The advantages of the filtered selection algorithms are: versatility (generalization), low complexity (no iteration). Independent of a classifier (Wang et al. 2018), faster than wrapper method (Suto et al. 2017) (Chan et al. 2020). The filter method is the best method for large size dataset, since it ignores the correlation between features that affects performance. (Jamabi & Kadhim, 2018). Human Activity Recognition (HAR) can be used to anticipate and detect anomalous behaviour patterns (Yazdansepas et al. 2016), provide personalized health services (Banos et al. 2012), and is applied in chronic disease management, rehabilitation systems and disease preventions (Ni et al. 2016). HAR plays major roles in public healthcare and well-being., and promises to provide automatic technological health monitoring for elderly living independently (Banos et al. 2012) (Yazdansepas et al. 2016). Vision based technologies have been used for HAR. Some disadvantages of vision based methods includes, expensive hardware, computationally intensive, video analytics, limited monitoring and limited portability (Yazdansepas et al. 2016). Due to their small size and relatively low cost, accelerometers can be embedded into wrist bands, watches, bracelets belts, and smartphones (Ni et al. 2016), generally classified as wearables. Modern Smartphones are embedded with a lot of sensors, which makes them ideal for monitoring human activities (Capela et al. 2015). A lot of work has been done on sensor and smartphone-based activity recognition, however more research work is required to obtain better accuracy with reduced computation cost. One way of obtaining such gain is in reducing the number of features required to improve model accuracy compared to existing works. One major aspect of HAR which this work explores is feature selection. This research work performs a comparative analysis to several filter-based FS methods to understand their effectiveness for classification with relevant features that reduced computational complexity to HAR problems. This work analyses which features are most relevant for each activity and further investigates which classifier provides the best accuracy with those features. The study is crucial to provide researchers with a guide of the most relevant features for activity recognition along-side the best classifiers. The effectiveness of selected features is measured in this research work.

2.0 RELATED WORKS

Using three filter-based feature selection (chi-square, Fisher-Score, and Relief-F) Chen et al. 2020 investigated activity recognition with postural transition awareness, and adopted three classifiers (SVM, DT, RF) for comparative analysis. Features in time and frequency domains (total of 585 features) were extracted. SVM out-performed the other classifiers in the various subset features obtained by the

three feature selection methods, with best results up to 98% on the multi-class classification. According to the analysis of the classification results there are no significant differences between the classification accuracy of the three sets of features. Considering three types of population: able bodied, elderly and stroke patients Capela et al. 2015 extracted seventy-six features. Relief-F, correlation-based feature selection, fast correlation-based filter feature selection methods were used to select subsets of features. Three generic classifiers (Naive Bayes, support vector machines, J48 decision trees) were used to evaluate these feature subsets. Six activities class: sit, stand, lie, large movements, stairs, and small movements were considered. Fan et al. 2019 used the threshold classification method, DT, SVM and Gaussian process to evaluate the classification accuracy of selected features using filter-based method (Fisher-Score, Relief-F and Chi-square). A total of 585 features from accelerometer and gyroscope in the time and frequency domain were extracted. Six activities and postural transitions were considered. An average accuracy of 96.4% was obtained with the reduced feature sets, thereby reducing the model building time. To reduce the dimension of the dataset, Yazdansepas et al. 2016 used Relief-based, correlation based and expert selection to extract more discriminant features. Six classifiers RF, KNN, DT, MLP, and SVM, NB were used to evaluate the feature set, RF out-performed other classifiers with an average accuracy of 83.7%. It was observed that MLP was not affected with the feature selection, while other classifiers were affected. To analyse which features are most relevant for each activity and investigates which classifiers provide the best accuracy with these features, Espirillia et al.2018 used two feature selection methods (consistency measure and dependence measure) with five classifiers (NB, KNN, Multi-Layer Perception (MLP), DT, SVM). Six different scenarios were considered self-care, house cleaning, exercise sports and food preparation. KNN was the best classifier for the various scenarios. The common features for the six scenarios were considered as the most discriminant features.

Ni et al. (2016), used three filter methods IG, CFS and Best Fast Search (BFS), and Relief-F to extract important features in a feature set of 77 features. Using a 10fold cross validation, KNN, J48, MLP, NB and SVM classifiers were used to evaluate the generated subset of features. RF contributed highest accuracy of 95.62% on the input obtained by using charge detection-based segmentation. CFS and BFS algorithm selected a subset feature containing 21 feature and that provided the highest accuracy (**Ni et al. 2016**).

Erdas et al. 2016 used chi-square, CFS, Relief-F, Info Gain and Gain Ratio for feature selection, and RF, KNN and SVM classifiers to test the effectiveness of the system. Best accuracy was reported by RF in the time domain. An ensemble feature selection reduced the dominant features to 16 and also improve the accuracy. Most work review here did not implement up to the basic six classifiers in supervised machine learning. In the area of HAR which has become an active research area, little work has been done on such comparison, and more work is required o as to effectively recognize activity with reduced computational complexities. The basic sic classifiers are considered in this work, as well as more FS methods than found in most works. Also this present work adapts a dataset with transitive activities which is neglected in most works.

Figure 1: Frame work for Feature selection

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials and methods for this research are discussed in this section.

3.1 Methods

The study investigates the differences among filter-based feature selection techniques, and exploring the contribution of each one and its effectiveness against classification accuracy. The comparison tested was done with respect to classification accuracy for DT, KNN, MLP, SVM, NB and RF. First, all six classifiers were used to evaluate the dataset based on all features available. After which the five feature selection techniques are applied to the dataset. Each of the techniques ranked the feature based on their performance. This step aims to evaluate the effectiveness of reduced subsets of metrics. Different thresholds were used in the classification systems and their effects on accuracy compared. The research determines which classification algorithm and feature selection combination produces the better results. In this study, experiment was performed using 10 folds' cross validation implemented in the WEKA machine learning tool. The first 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 and 100 features were selected and the result with six classifiers are presented,

3.2 Dataset

Jorge et al. 2015 collected sensor data with a group of 30 volunteers within an age bracket of 19-48 years. Performing six basic activities: three static postures (standing, sitting, lying) and three dynamic activities (walking, walking downstairs and walking upstairs). The experiment also included postural

transitions that occurred between the static postures. Which are: stand-to-sit, sit-to-stand, sit-to-lie, lie-to-sit, stand-to-lie, and lie-to-stand. All the participants were wearing a smartphone (Samsung Galaxy S II) on the waist during the experiment execution. The experiment captured 3-axial linear acceleration and 3-axial angular velocity at a constant rate of 50Hz using the embedded accelerometer and gyroscope of the device. The experiments were video-recorded to label the data manually Jorge et al. 2015.

3.3 Framework

3.4 Data preprocessing

Jorge et al. 2015 transformed THE SIGNAL into samples with fixed-width sliding windows of 2.56 seconds and 50% overlap (i.e. 128 readings/window). The raw data is also processed to reduce noise using median filter of order 5 in each dimension separately. On the basis of an assumption that the gravity acceleration only has low frequency components, a Butterworth low-pass filter with 0.3 Hz cut-off frequency was applied to sensor total acceleration signals to separate the body (B) and gravity (g) accelerations. Besides, from the 3-axial total Acceleration (A), body acceleration (B) and Gyro signals (G), jerk and signal magnitudes are calculated.

3.5 Feature Extraction

A feature vector consists of both time-domain features as well as frequency-domain features were calculated on each windowed data. The extracted features were obtained by processing the acceleration values of X-, Y-, and Z-axis of both BA component and GA component. Commonly used time-domain statistical features, such as mean, root mean squared, standard deviation and correlation coefficient were used in this **work** (Jorge et al. 2015). In this research, we applied various filter-based FS methods to rank the entire features, and the first 40 ranked features are shown in table 1.

/ no	CF		Relief F		IG		GR		Chi-Square	
	Rank	Feature	Rank	Feature	Rank	Feature	Rank	Feature	Rank	Feature
1	0.41227	367	0.3297185	57			0.5756	350	18469.53658	382
2	0.41015	368	0.248669	51	1.382371	382	0.5746	363	17790.303641	1
3	0.40923	103	0.2485942	367	1.3500858	390	0.5746	86	17722.283554	390
4	0.40851	235	0.235366	53	1.3182786	272	0.5571	99	16629.900597	504
5	0.40687	288	0.2317901	559	1.3165273	311	0.5443	419	16319.530831	394

6	0.40662	105	0.22926	42	1.3114526	10	0.538 4	102	15966.85 2525	97
7	0.40624	524	0.2291192	368	1.3056711	282	0.538 2	89	15958.86 3664	311
8	0.40558	104	0.227604 8	235	1.305664 5	4	0.530 6	353	15895.814 355	10
9	0.4036	369	0.226806 6	288	1.303610 3	315	0.528 1	423	15786.247 855	84
1 0	0.40092	289	0.226655 3	41	1.3029919	303	0.5134	105	15784.521 393	361
11	0.39875	185	0.212404	103	1.300360 5	394	0.512 8	531	15706.515 384	272
12	0.39816	511	0.200854 2	289	1.296682 7	266	0.5071	356	15678.861 757	345
13	0.39722	290	0.199825 1	50	1.2958713	269	0.506 3	95	15598.49 2405	7
14	0.39684	281	0.197830 8	104	1.287789 6	7	0.506 3	341	15596.187 482	23
15	0.39488	550	0.196206 1	54	1.2861493	97	0.501 8	228	15529.235 681	303
16	0.39404	448	0.195374 5	524	1.2853715	17	0.500 6	344	15487.916 071	87
17	0.39317	267	0.193494 8	261	1.2808411	84	0.500 3	142	15477.426 683	266
1 8	0.3931	273	0.192503 7	511	1.280759 6	361	0.498 2	333	15468.34 4877	4
19	0.39203	88	0.188849 8	560	1.278240 4	345	0.494 9	517	15465.20 8126	282
2 0	0.39055	261	0.186539 2	369	1.2750191	87	0.494 9	335	15401.850 471	348
21	0.39054	227	0.183992 2	58	1.264792 4	348	0.493 3	347	15468.46 3567	315
2 2	0.39054	232	0.183035 5	222	1.2563479	304	0.491 3	518	15325.48 6439	100
2 3	0.39031	346	0.183035 5	209	1.2555439	275	0.490 6	523	15310.934 066	216
2 4	0.39017	447	0.1828715	105	1.2542919	351	0.489 1	129	15310.934 066	503

25	0.39007	96	0.1776343	10	1.2519322	504	0.4881	231	15306.059012	506
26	0.38991	85	0.1764598	65	1.2489578	354	0.4875	411	15192.793939	96
27	0.38942	446	0.1717463	185	1.2477334	234	0.4868	524	15184.505862	269

Table 1: First 40 Features returned by the five FS methods

28	0.38886	101	0.1674517	446	1.2458916	90	0.4867	366	15179.933083	354
29	0.38883	352	0.166026	290	1.2452814	229	0.4865	420	15166.543809	232
30	0.3883	53	0.164944	183	1.2414023	100	0.486	12	15166.543809	227
31	0.38791	360	0.1607676	64	1.2406897	96	0.4806	480	15118.480769	351
32	0.38785	183	0.1604374	550	1.2402917	233	0.4805	416	15087.065218	304
33	0.38743	272	0.159331	448	1.2400969	232	0.4785	234	14762.427433	17
34	0.38713	349	0.1576426	269	1.2400969	227	0.4773	432	14633.712231	275
35	0.38651	266	0.1570274	273	1.2369128	235	0.4767	101	14565.315942	233
36	0.38612	439	0.1557446	537	1.2312375	288	0.4751	368	14560.314657	90
37	0.38474	184	0.1533617	4	1.225192	360	0.4732	522	14546.771273	2
38	0.38468	87	0.1532779	272	1.2238485	367	0.4725	399	14530.150166	54
39	0.38418	245	0.1532769	447	1.2200157	383	0.4722	519	14524.081026	367
40	0.38418	240	0.1470616	184	1.2182504	522	0.4713	476	14491.650576	220

.6Filter based Feature selection

3.6.1 Chi-Squared (CHIS) s

Chi-square determines the influence of features on classification based on the degree of deviation between observed values and theoretical inferred values. The basic formula of the chi-square test is as follows in equation 1(Janabi & Kadhim, 2018):

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(A-T)^2}{T} \tag{1}$$

Where A is the actual (observed) frequency, T is the theoretical (expected) frequency, and χ^2 is the chi-square value.

3.6.2 Correlation based Feature Selection (CFS)

This algorithm computes the correlation between all features and the output class and selects the best feature subset (i.e. the subset with features highly correlated with the class variable and have low correlation with each other features) using correlation based heuristic evaluation function. CFS’s feature subset evaluation function is: CFS is given by the equation 2(Janabi & Kadhim, 2018).

$$M_s = \frac{k \bar{r}_{cf}}{\sqrt{k + k(k-1)r_{ff}}} \tag{2}$$

Where M_s is the heuristic “merit” of a feature subset S containing k features, r_{cf} is the mean feature-class correlation ($f \in S$) and r_{ff} is the average feature-feature inter-correlation.

3.6.3 ReliefF: The ReliefF algorithm randomly takes a sample R from the training sample set each time; finds k neighbor samples from the same sample set of the sample point R each time, finds k neighbor samples from different sample sets; and then randomly selects multiple sample points to update the feature weights, obtain the feature weight ranking, and set the threshold to select the effective features. It is adapted to work with multi-class problems by finding one or more (k) neighbouring instance M(C) from each different class C and averages their contribution for upgrading estimates W[A] weighting it with the prior probability of each class. The estimation of weight W of feature A when the sampled instance is R (which is sampled m times) and the nearest instance of the same class is H is conducted as shown in Equation 3 (Janabi & Kadhim, 2018).

$$W[A] := W[A] - \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{diff(A,R,H_j)}{m.k} + \sum_{C \neq class(R)} \frac{P(C)}{1-P(class(R_i))} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{diff(A,R,M_j(C))}{m.k} \quad (3)$$

The difference of numeric features is calculated as shown in Equation 4.

$$diff(A, I_1, I_2) = \frac{|value(A, I_1) - value(A, I_2)|}{\max(A) - \min(A)} \quad (4)$$

3.6.4 Information Gain (IG): This metric is based on change of information entropy that would occur if the state of the information would change and can be calculated by subtracting conditional entropy of the class from its entropy. Entropy of a feature C is calculated as shown in Equation 5. Conditional entropy of a feature C if the state of feature A is given is calculated as shown in Equation 6: (Janabi & Kadhim, 2018)

$$H(C) = - \sum_{i=1}^n P(C = c_i) \log_2(P(C = c_i)) \quad (5)$$

$$H(C|A) = - \sum_{j=1}^k P(A = a_j) H(C|A = a_j) \quad (6)$$

Where $P(C = c_i)$ is relative appearance frequency of value c_i in feature C in the data set, $H(C|A = a_j)$ is the entropy of feature C in the data subset where the value of attribute A is a_j .

3.6.5 Gain Ratio is based on Information Gain metric and eliminates the weakness that occurs in data sets that have features with large numbers of unique values which are given preference over other possibly better features with fewer values. Therefore, Gain Ratio divides Information Gain by entropy of considered feature as shown in Equation 7. (Janabi & Kadhim, 2018)

$$GR(C, A) = \frac{H(C) - H(C|A)}{H(A)} \quad (7)$$

3.7 Supervised Machine Learning Classifiers

3.7.1. Naive Bayes classifier

Naïve Bayes classifier is a simple probabilistic classifier with assumption of independence among attributes. This classifier learns from training data and predicting the class of the test instance with higher posterior probability. Let $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_l\}$ be the set of l classes, and let $W = \{w_1, \dots, w_m\}$ be the set of features enclosed in these classes. Given a new document d, the probability that d belongs to class c_i is given by Bayes rule in equation 8,

$$P(C = c | X = x) = \frac{p(C=c)p(X=x|C=c)}{p(X=x)} \quad (8)$$

Predicts the most probable class according to class probabilities that are calculated for class set C

3.7.2. K-nearest neighbor (IBK)

In k-NN classification, the output is a class membership. An object is classified by a majority vote of its neighbors, with the object being assigned to the class most common among its k nearest neighbors. For example, given a regularization parameter k and an example x, the k-NN technique considers the k training examples closest to x according to their distance in the feature space $\{0, 1\}^K$ and gives as predicted class the dominant real class among those k examples.

3.7.3 SVM builds a function of relevant features by assigning weights to them (irrelevant features are assigned weight 0) based on relevant instances (support vectors). The function is a hyperplane in the instance space that separates different classes with a maximum margin (distance from the hyperplane to the nearest instances).

3.7.4 DT. The trees are constructed from a data set by dividing the training set into subset until a class value can be assigned to each subset. The tree construction starts with choosing a root node representing a feature that splits the initial data set into subsets according to its values. Then nodes are selected for the second level split and so on. The features are chosen based on evaluation using Gain Ratio.

3.7.5 Random Forest is an ensemble of random trees. Random trees are constructed considering a predefined number of randomly chosen features.

3.7.6: Linear Regression

The basic idea of linear regression classification (LRC) is to find the best class reconstruction for test samples; that is, the class with the best class reconstruction is regarded as the class of test samples (Fan et al. 2019).

4.0 Experimental Results and Discussion

The experiments have been implemented using the Weka software. For both feature selection methods and all classification algorithms, the default parameters of Weka have been used. The experimental results are provided in this section...

4.1 Results

Figure 2a: Decision Tree Accuracy

Figure 2b: BN Classifier Accuracy

Figure 2C: KNN Accuracy

Figure 2D: LR Accuracy

Figure 2e: RF Accuracy

Figure2f: SVM Accuracy

From figure 2a to 2f, the various response of the six classifiers on the number of feature returned is shown. For most FS methods, the behaviors of the FS methods are similar. Also, the accuracy improves on the FS until it gets to the optimal feature set, after which changes in the accuracy is marginal. Summary performance of RF classifier is as follow, correctly classified instances are 7516, which is 96.7684 %, while, incorrectly classified instances are 251 which is 3.2316 %. The kappa statistic is 0.9617, mean absolute error is 0.0268, root mean squared error is, 0.0843, Relative absolute error is 19.0322 %, root relative squared error is 31.7783 % and total number of instances is 7767. Figure 3, demonstrates the accuracy of the classifiers on the various feature selection methods.

Figure 3: Classification Accuracy from each feature Selector

The detailed statistic of each activity class is shown in table 2 and performance of each classifier on the various scenario is given in table 3.

Table 2: Detailed Accuracy by Class

TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Class
0.992	0.001	0.993	0.992	0.993	0.991	1.000	1.000	WALKING
0.990	0.003	0.979	0.990	0.984	0.982	1.000	0.999	WALKING_UPSTAIRS
0.987	0.002	0.985	0.987	0.986	0.984	1.000	0.999	WALKING_DOWNSTAIRS
0.952	0.008	0.959	0.952	0.956	0.947	0.998	0.993	SITTING
0.966	0.009	0.959	0.966	0.963	0.954	0.999	0.995	STANDING
0.999	0.001	0.995	0.999	0.997	0.997	1.000	0.999	LAYING
0.809	0.001	0.792	0.809	0.800	0.799	0.999	0.865	STAND_TO_SIT
0.826	0.000	1.000	0.826	0.905	0.909	1.000	0.947	SIT_TO_STAND
0.733	0.003	0.714	0.733	0.724	0.721	0.998	0.799	SIT_TO_LIE
0.700	0.003	0.667	0.700	0.683	0.681	0.997	0.660	LIE_TO_SIT
0.700	0.003	0.759	0.700	0.728	0.726	0.997	0.799	STND_TO_LIE
0.526	0.002	0.667	0.526	0.588	0.590	0.988	0.604	LIE_TO_STAND
0.968	0.004	0.967	0.968	0.967	0.963	0.999	0.987	Weighted Avg

Table3: Performance of Classifiers

Classifier	Original Data	After Relief	After Info Gain	After Gain Ratio	After Correlation	After Chi Square
Baysnet	79.5	86	79.9	56.5	59.1	82.4

KNN	96.1	95.8	92.2	93.2	86.9	94.6
Regression	96	95.6	93.1	83.6	86.1	95.1
J48	93	93.6	90.9	77	79.9	92.8
RF	96.8	96.8	94.5	86.1	88.4	95.3
SVM	86.6	91.3	87.4	69.9	75.2	89

Since RF gives the highest accuracy, the confusion matrix is shown in table 4. It can be seen that most activities were correctly classified, the misclassified cases were mainly in activities such sitting and standing, Lie_To_Sit, Stand_To_Lie and Lie_To_Stand. The misclassified cases is mainly due to similarities in these activities.

Table 4: Confusion Matrix for Random Forest Classification

A	b	C	d	E	F	g	h	I	J	k	l	Classified as
1216	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	a = WALKING
3	1062	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	b= WALKING_UPSTAIRS
4	9	974	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	c= WALKING_DOWNSTAIRS
0	0	0	1231	56	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	d = SITTING
0	0	0	49	1374	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	e = STANDING
0	0	0	0	0	1412	0	0	0	0	0	1	f = LAYING
0	5	1	0	1	0	38	0	1	0	1	0	g = STAND_TO_SIT
0	0	0	1	0	0	2	19	0	0	1	0	h = SIT_TO_STAND
0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	55	0	18	0	i = SIT_TO_LIE
0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	1	42	0	14	j = LIE_TO_SIT
1	3	0	1	1	1	2	0	18	0	63	0	k = STAND_TO_LIE
0	1	1	0	0	2	0	0	2	21	0	30	l = LIE_TO_STAND

4.2 Discussion

In this paper, a comparative investigation of five filter-based feature selection methods and the effectiveness of the method was evaluated using six machine learning classifiers was performed. Among the used feature selection techniques, relief with random forest classifier out-performed the rest and is recommended. It was observed that feature selection techniques affect the accuracy of the classifiers and reduces model building time. The analysis results presented in this paper are based on the selection of certain classification algorithms and some performance measures. We have used various confusion matrix parameters to evaluate the performance of feature selection methods. According to the results, more features do not guarantee performance improvement, the performance of machine learning algorithms is feature selection dependent, and a relationship exists between machine learning and feature selection algorithms. The RF algorithm was the classification

algorithm that provided the highest accuracy. This experimentation applies ReliefF feature selection method and the training process was carried out with the set of features. Some features were common to all feature selection methods, and these features are considered very important in the original dataset, to identify all the activities. In general terms, the six classifiers performed better with those features selected than on the raw dataset. Regarding the classifiers, it was clearly demonstrated that the classifier performing best, in terms of overall classification accuracy, was RF.

4.3 Related Study

Rodriguez et al. 2007 performed an investigation using feature selection algorithms with three filter models and three wrapper models and concluded that the reduced datasets maintained the prediction capability with fewer attributes than the original datasets.

Liu and Yu provided a survey of feature selection algorithms and presented an integrated approach of intelligent feature selection. The study evaluation criteria, and data mining tasks, reveal unattempt combinations, and provides guidelines in selecting feature selection algorithms.

The limitation of the studies discussed above is that no systematic comparative study was performed to evaluate the effectiveness of different feature selection techniques. In addition, very few studies have investigated feature selection techniques in the context of HAR prediction. Hence, it is needed to evaluate the performance of the feature selection techniques for HAR datasets also to understand how well these feature selection techniques handle and best manage the different challenges posed by it. This study, compares the performance of five feature selection techniques in the context of HAR. To validate the effectiveness of the feature selection techniques, we use six classifiers and evaluate the prediction models using some performance measures,

6. Conclusions and Future Works

The experiment analyzed to distinguish which features are the most relevant and which classifier provided the highest accuracy with those features. To do so, five feature selection methods have been applied in conjunction with six well-known classification algorithms (NB, KNN, LR, RF, DT, SVM). Considering this experimentation, the most relevant and non-relevant features for scenarios have been identified. This paper has presented a benchmark comparison of five feature selection techniques that produce ranked lists of attributes. The benchmark shows that in general, attribute selection is beneficial for improving the performance of common learning algorithms. It also shows that, like learning algorithms, there is no single best approach for all situations. What is needed by the data miner is not only an understanding of how different attribute selection techniques work, but also the strengths and weaknesses of the target learning algorithm. We found that the performance of the feature selection techniques is varied with the classifiers used. The goal in this research is to Compare and contrast different feature selection methods against the mentioned high dimensional data set and a reference data set. Filter based methods were applied to these data sets, and their results are compared and analyzed. The classification accuracy achieved by each method is compared against the better feature selection method found.

REFERENCES

- Banos, O., Damas, M., Pomares, H., Prieto, A., & Rojas, I. (2012). Daily living activity recognition based on statistical feature quality group selection. *Expert Systems with Applications Elsevier*, 39, 8013–8021.
- Capela, NA., Lemaire, ED., & Baddour, N. (2015). Feature Selection for Wearable Smartphone-Based Human Activity Recognition with Able bodied, Elderly, and Stroke Patients. *PLOS ONE* 10(4) : e0124414, 10(4), 1-18,
- Chen, L., Fan, S., Kumar, V., & Jia, Y. (2020) A Method of Human Activity Recognition in Transitional Period. *Information, MDPI*, 11, 416; doi: 10.3390/info11090416
- Erdaş, CB. Atasoy, I., Açıcı, K., & Oğul, H. . . (2016). Integrating features for accelerometer based activity recognition. *Procedia Computer Science* 98 (2016) 522 – 527.
- Espinilla, M., Medina, J., Salguero, A., Irvine, N., Donnelly, M., Cleland, I., & Nugent, C. (2018) Human Activity Recognition from the Acceleration Data of a Wearable Device. Which Features Are More Relevant by Activities? *Proceedings*, 2, 1242; doi: 10.3390/proceedings2191242
- Fan, S., Yating Jia, Y., & Jia, C. (2019). A Feature Selection and Classification Method for ctivity Recognition based on an Inertial Sensing Unit. *Information* 2019, 10, 290;
- Gao, K., Khoshgoftaar, T., & Van Hulse, JV. (2010). An Evaluation of Sampling on Filter-Based Feature Selection Methods. *Proceedings of the Twenty-Third International Florida Artificial Intelligence Research Society Conference (FLAIRS 2010)*
- Huan, L. (2005). Toward integrating feature selection algorithms for classification and clustering. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 17(4):491–502.
- Janabi, KBS. & Kadhim, R, (2018). Data Reduction Techniques: A comparative Study for attribute selection methods. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Technology*, 8(1),
- [Jorge,L., Ortiz,R., Oneto, L., Samà, A., Parra, X., & Anguita, D. (2015). Transition-aware human activity recognition using smartphones. *Neurocomputing*. Springer.
- Khaire, UM. & Dhanalakshmi, R. Stability of feature selection algorithm: A review. (2019). *Journal of King Saud University – Computer and Information Sciences*,

- Ni, Q., Patterson, T, Cleland, I., & Nugent, C... (2016). Dynamic detection of window starting positions and its implementation within an activity recognition framework *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 62, 171-180, Elsevier Inc.
- Rodriguez, D., Ruiz, R., Cuadrado-Gallego, J., Aguilar-Ruiz, J., & Garre. M. (2007). Attribute selection in software engineering datasets for detecting fault modules. In *Proceedings of the 33rd EUROMICRO Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications, EUROMICRO*, 418–423.
- Suto, J., Oniga, S., & Sitar, PP. (2017). Feature analysis to human activity recognition. *International Journal of Computers Communications & Control*, ISSN 1841-9836, 12(1), 116-130.
- Venkatesh, B., & Anuradha, J. A review of feature selection and its methods. (2019). *Cybernetics and Information Technologies*, 19(1), Sofia, ISSN: 1314-4081,
- Wang, H., Ke, R' Li, J., an, Y., Wang, K., & Yu, L. (2018). A correlation-based binary particle swarm optimization method for feature selection in human activity recognition. *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, 14(4),
- Yazdansepas, D., Niazi AH., Gay, JL., Maier,FW., Ramaswamy, L., Rasheed, K., & Buman, MP. (2016). A multi-featured a p proach for wearable sensor-based h uman activity recognition. *IEEE International Conference on Healthcare Informatics*.